

Middle East University

Faculty of Education

METHODS, FACILITIES AND MATERIALS IN A KINDERGARTEN 3
MONTESSORI VS NON-MONTESSORI CLASSROOMS IN BEIRUT,
LEBANON: EFFECTS ON STUDENT LEARNING

A Thesis

Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the

Requirements for the Degree

Master of Arts in Education

by

Nathalie J. Char

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THESIS ABSTRACT

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Preschool is one of the major foundations for students to become students who enjoy learning, and are good critical thinkers and problem solvers. To help our students develop toward this goal, we should have a good plan regarding how to teach them. That is why schools should carefully choose the methodology they want to follow to be able to offer the best to their students. To be able to implement Montessori and active learning we need to have facilities, manipulatives and materials. Schools that follow methodologies that use active learning such as Montessori have certain advantages in reaching this goal. But do they actually produce different learning results?

In this thesis we will see how a Montessori school that does active learning activities and uses different senses while teaching and how a school that does not follow Montessori are different, and how the students' outcomes were significantly different. The achievement test results showed better ability in the Montessori school

students in reading and general knowledge and that students' scores were almost the same in critical thinking and memory.

"Thanks be to God, who gives us the victory through our Lord Jesus Christ."

—1 Corinthians 15:57

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Student learning is one of the most important goals for teachers, even in kindergarten. Teachers teach so that students will learn. One of the things that affects learning is kindergarten. Kindergarten is a class for 5-year-old children to start learning the basics before they go to Grade 1 and start their formal education. “Kindergarten provides universal access to early childhood education that is key to ensuring that children are socially and developmentally ready to begin the more formal learning process that begins with Grade 1” (Elementary Teachers Federation of Ontario, 2001, p. 5).

Teachers want their students to be good performers and learners. The more they can grasp, the more the teacher can teach them. It is important for students to arrive at school with some foundations to learn, and this is the work of preschool and kindergarten, also called early childhood education. Research has shown that early childhood education makes a difference in students’ elementary school results. Fully “41 percent of students who did not attend an early education program had low performance in mathematics, while only 24 percent of students who attended more than one year of preschool were low performers” (Camera, 2016, para. 14). The concept of constructivism reminds us of the importance of students building their knowledge on previous ideas to understand it and learn better. This shows why KG3 is important for our students.

School activities that emphasize active learning are not only enjoyable, but they help students see the importance of what they are studying and how will it be used in life. “Hands-on activities let the students' minds grow and learn based on the experiences and the environment they are exposed to” (Lizardi, n.d., para. 2). This sort of applied learning helps students learn more. As Confucius said, “I hear and I forget. I see and I remember. I do and I understand.” The more the students apply what they learn the more they can grasp. The pyramid below (Figure 1) shows that students learn 75% of what they practice by doing. In participatory teaching methods where the students are actively involved in discovery, they learn half of the information given to them, whereas, they grasp less than 50% when using passive teaching methods. This graphic demonstrates why active learning is important. It matters how we teach.

Figure 1. The learning pyramid.

Note: Adapted from Stanley, J. (2013). *Understanding the learning pyramid*. Retrieved from <http://www.thephuketnews.com/understanding-the-learning-pyramid-40899.php>

Maria Montessori, Jerome Bruner, Jean Piaget, and many others have written about the importance of manipulatives in classrooms especially for young children (for example, see McLeod, 2012, Montessori Northwest, 2015; North American Montessori Center, 2007). Manipulatives can help our students learn by working with their own hands. When students work with their own hands and are offered a real experience they will be able to make sense of what they are learning and they will learn more. When students see why a specific activity is relevant to their lives, they will learn it better. And as we saw in Figure 1, students learn more when they practice actively, and our goal as teachers is to make sure our students are gaining and learning in the best way. With manipulatives we can implement hands-on activities and we will be able to make sure students are learning. That is why schools should be proactive and take some steps in preschools to ensure that students learn as much as possible. Schools should have facilities that help teachers teach and students learn and they should make sure that teachers are following methodologies that allow for active learning.

When teachers do their work well, and classes are rich with materials that make the class vivid and enjoyable, the students will feel motivated to learn more and more. Learning is affected not just by how intelligent students are, or whether they come to school ready to learn. “Level of achievement is [also] affected by choice, effort and persistence. The higher these indices, the higher the motivation and the more likely task achievement will occur” (Hurst, n.d., Motivation section, para. 7). This means that the better the teachers’ methodology, and the better the use of materials, the higher the motivation, and the more the motivation, the better the achievement.

Unfortunately, some schools are missing motivated teachers, good methodologies, manipulatives and other resources, and a focused curriculum. When

these are not optimum, this affects students' learning negatively (see for example Lyons, n.d.).

Many schools and teachers have given up using manipulatives in class. "Fifteen percent of kindergarten teachers said they spent three or more hours per day on teacher-directed whole-class activities in 1998. In 2010, that figure had more than doubled to 32 percent" (Samuels, 2015, p. 2). Facilities that are in poor condition have negative effects on students as well. Schools should make sure to have classrooms well suited to teaching and learning. If schools have no heating, for example, students will not be able to concentrate. When a school moved from one category to another (from poor to fair, or from fair to excellent), "research has shown that "student achievement scores could be expected to increase by 5.455 percentage points" (OSSTF/FEESO, n.d., p.9). This means the physical environment of the school affects how the students learn.

The students who were surveyed also agreed that the condition of their school building had an impact on their motivation. They also agreed that "most students would learn more and achieve at higher levels if the schools they attended were in good physical condition." Finally, a significant number (24 out of 39) of students believed that a teacher would be more effective in a better environment. (Edwards, 2006, p.142)

After seeing both a study done on the physical environment of a school and also what students think about it, we are able to see that the environment of the school does affect both the students and the teachers. Maslow's hierarchy of needs shows that some needs are more important than others. If our students are distracted by noise, colors, or other things, they will not be able to concentrate. (e.g., Earthman, & Lemasters, 2009). Maslow believes that some need are primary to others, because if the students does not feel safe he will not be able to have the feeling of belonging, and if the students don't

have the feeling of belonging they will not be able to have good self-esteem. So when a student feels safe and that the surrounding environment is well prepared to motivate him/her and help with concentration, the students will be able to be more affective in what they will be doing next. This also affects the students' achievement.

Manipulatives and facilities have a major impact on students, however, some schools are not well prepared. A research study done by Allen (2007) about using manipulatives while teaching math with one group and not using manipulatives with a second group showed that manipulatives make a difference. "Although, the null hypotheses cannot be rejected at a .05 significant level, this researcher can say that there was a significant change in the experimental group scores over the control group scores, with an 85% confidence level" (p. 12).

Some teachers give up on using manipulatives because of fear or low self-efficacy. In addition, some schools are investing in technology because of its high demand in the world around us (e.g., Spencer, 2012). If the schools don't invest in facilities, teachers cannot implement active learning if there are no manipulatives in their classes.

Schools also need a clear curriculum to guide them and their teachers so they will know what to teach, and what is expected of them. When there is a clear curriculum, teachers can teach toward a clear goal, knowing what they are trying to accomplish with their efforts. Without curriculum goals, there is no urgency to use specific methods or facilities, as there is no required direction.

The Lebanese curriculum, created by the republic of Lebanon's Ministry of Education and Higher Education (1997) states the importance of learning and how we can make our students better being and shows some general themes to follow but no actual studies. Kindergartens are only briefly included even though it is one of the most

important stages in school. Schools must work mainly on their own to make sure to have good methodologies, materials, and goals in kindergarten to help students gain educationally and socially to be ready for Grade 1 and its governmental curriculum. Though methodologies can differ between schools, the specific goal of helping students learn and get ready for Grade 1 must be the focus of any kindergarten program (see for example Camera, 2016; Shappee, 2015). Whether this is specifically stated or not, this is an underlying goal of any kindergarten curriculum.

Given the trend mentioned above of paying less attention to active learning materials (e.g., Earthman & Lemasters, 2009) coupled with the limited guidance from the Lebanese government to preschools, how can schools make sure that their students are prepared for Grade 1? Do materials really make a measurable difference? How much difference do methods make? How much difference do facilities make? Are these differences measurable?

Problem Statement

Every teacher's purpose and goal of teaching is to make sure that her students learn what she is teaching in the best and easiest way. But not all methods yield the same results. Differential use of materials also is said to affect learning. There is a need to see if methodologies and facilities actually affect preschool learning and if the differential approaches use materials differently. Is there a measurable difference in actual academic outcomes in preschool classrooms using a Montessori or non-Montessori approach while teaching in Lebanon?

Research Questions

1. What are the facilities, materials and methodologies like in a Montessori schools setting? (Descriptive)

2. Are there differences in the use of materials and methodologies between a school using Montessori and a school not using it? (Qualitative)
3. Are there differences in preschool student outcomes between a Montessori school and a non-Montessori school? (*t*-test)
4. Do materials and the way they are used correlate with learning outcomes? (Qualitative)

Limitations and Delimitations

This study worked with two schools only. Though there are many schools with different methodologies, I focused on only two of them because of limitations of time. Gaining access to two of schools is also easier than getting access to more schools.

There are some problems that will be faced while working on this thesis. One of these problems is that there are a lot of schools that follow Montessori. By taking only two schools, we will see a minority, not the majority. Approaches to teaching also might differ in different regions in Lebanon, but this study works with two schools from the same district. In addition, there are a lot of different methodologies that can improve learning but here I chose only one of them to be studied. Moreover, we might not be able to differentiate which affects outcomes more: the methodology, or the use of facilities, or manipulatives. On the other hand, they work in parallel with each other, so we might not need to divide them.

Who Might Be Interested?

This study compares and contrasts two different teaching methodologies and shows how schools can improve students' learning and get students ready for Grade 1. This study could help first of all every head of section that needs to know how to improve kindergarten. Second, it may help coordinators and give them ideas to make

sure their teachers are following good teaching strategies. It would also help principals to see different schools methodologies and how to improve their school's reputation because of the good way of teaching. It will also help every teacher to gain ideas about how to actively teach their students and make sure that they are learning and enjoying it.

Definition of Terms

Montessori: A system of education for young children that seeks to develop natural interests and activities rather than use formal teaching methods.

Methods: In this study, *method* is used to mean a particular procedure of teaching for accomplishing or approaching students learning, especially a systematic or established one.

School Facilities: School facilities includes indoor and outdoor spaces, manipulatives in classrooms, boards, projectors, laptops, centers, resources for both teachers and students, etc.

Manipulatives: Any of various objects or materials that students can touch and move around in order to help them learn mathematical and other concepts: the use of blocks, flashcards, and other objects in the classroom.

Active Learning: A process whereby students engage in activities, such as reading, writing, discussion, or problem solving that promote analysis, synthesis, and evaluation of class content.

Academic success: Students' educational achievement. The satisfaction and acquisition of desired knowledge, skills and competencies, of educational outcomes.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

The effects of facilities and materials on early childhood learning have been studied extensively in the past. This chapter will review research done on the importance of active learning in early childhood and how it can help our students learn more. We will review how materials and facilities help in active teaching, and we will look at the history of two different approaches to teaching, to see how these two methodologies might have different effects on our students' learning. Since this study is being done in Lebanon we will be also seeing the Lebanese curriculum and if it helps or not the schools in what they should be teaching in preschools and what does the curriculum show about preschool in general.

Early Childhood Education

Early childhood education is a branch of education theory which relates to the teaching of young children up until the age of about eight. These years lay the basis for subsequent development because they help the child develop social, emotional, cognitive and physical needs - to establish a solid and broad foundation for lifelong learning and wellbeing. "Children learn best when early childhood care and education (ECCE) is child-centered, play-based and collaborative" (UNESCO Bangkok, n.d., para. 1). So early childhood education is the foundation to the child's development. To help the child develop properly our teaching should be child-centered and help him/her use all five senses to learn and have good foundations. When teachers offer students good education in their childhood, it will help them in later life regarding education and

social skills. Early education tackles not only academics but also psychological, psychomotor, and social skills. So it is very important to have a child-centered class for students to learn and grasp everything that is being taught in early childhood education. The more vivid the class, the more the students learn and the better beings they will become.

When we say *child-centered* it means the class should be enriched with active learning. To implement active learning we need safe environments, manipulatives, materials and facilities.

Active Learning

The foundation of this study on materials, methods, and facilities is a strong belief in active learning. If active learning is important, then there will be a need for space, manipulatives, and teaching approaches that encourage hands-on learning. For that reason, this review of literature begins with a section on active learning.

Active learning is a student-centered approach that helps students learn by applying what they are learning in various activities and building knowledge by the help and guidance of teachers. “Active learning is based on a theory of learning called constructivism, which emphasizes the fact that learners construct or build their own understanding” (Cambridge International Examination, n.d., What is the Theory Behind Active Learning section, para. 1).

In our classes as teachers, we have different types of students that learn differently, and when we use hands on activities, active learning and various activities, we will be able to reach more students than just lecturing.

“Active learning’ means students engage with the material, participate in the class, and collaborate with each other. Don't expect your students simply to

listen and memorize; instead, have them help demonstrate a process, analyze an argument, or apply a concept to a real-world situation.”(Stanford, n.d., para.1)

Teaching students actively is the best way a teacher can teach. As we said before, when students do some hands-on activities they will learn. That is why a teacher should give every student the opportunity to apply what they are learning and to relate it to his own real world. By doing so students will learn more than just sitting and listening to a lecture or memorizing.

“Research suggests that audience attention in lectures starts to wane every 10-20 minutes. Incorporating active learning techniques once or twice during a 50-minute class (twice or thrice for a 75-minute class) will encourage student engagement” (Cornell University Center for Teaching Excellence, 2012, Engaging students section, para. 2). This is even shorter with kindergartners. Good advice for working with this age group is, “be mindful of attention spans. Do not plan activities that last longer than 15 or 20 minutes. Use every-pupil-response techniques to ensure engagement, to keep young minds from wandering, and to help you monitor their understanding” (McKenna & Strauser, 2010).

Active learning not only helps students in their academics but it also helps them build a better self-esteem, and helps them think and improve some skills they have because students will have the chance to participate and feel engaged (Cornell University Center for Teaching Excellence, 2012).When we teach actively, we as teachers will be able to reach the students that are shy and help them talk; we can also reach the students that need extra help and we will be able to help them.

Different universities agree that active learning is important and helps students develop and improve (Cornell University Center for Teaching Excellence, 2012; The

University of Queensland, 2017). When a teacher uses active learning, she will be able to reach different learning styles and help most if not all her students learn in one way or another.

Active learning in kindergartens is all about drama playing, music, nature activities, or art. All the active learning activities will help students practice the core concepts they are learning. If they are studying about planting they can go and plant. If they are studying about music they can go to the music room and hear different notes.

The problem is that the use of active learning is decreasing. In recent years, researchers have found that some of the standard manipulative features of a typical kindergarten classroom simply are not there anymore. Teachers tend to enter to a class explains what she has and do activities on the books without any other activities that might cause students to walk around, to work in groups, or even use their senses, In addition, students are rarely being able to go outside and do some hands-on activities because of the burden of the curriculum. Active learning takes effort because a teacher needs to be able to manage her class while doing active learning. That might scare some teachers. In comparing older ways of teaching to what is being done nowadays, Samuels (2015) found that

The likelihood of having a water- or sand-table area fell from 49 percent to 25 percent. The presence of “dramatic play” areas fell from 87 percent to 57 percent. The likelihood of having a science or nature area fell from 64 percent to 42 percent. And the likelihood of having an art area dropped from 92 percent to 70 percent. (p. 2)

Moreover, we know that there are multiple intelligences, and that each student can succeed in a different way from the others. While using active learning, we can trigger all intelligences. However, active learning is also important for kindergartens.

Using hands-on activities in early childhood is a great way to link new concepts to ideas that children already understand. So active learning is significant in all ages starting preschool up till university students. The theory of constructivism is a foundation for active learning. It is a really helpful theory because it helps our students think and make links to be able to learn a new concept. This theory helps our students use their critical thinking and memory. Constructivism helps students review what they already have in their heads and add to them new concepts. This is what makes students grow, learn, and enjoy it. They are being an active part in constructing their learning with the hands on activities rather than hearing and memorizing. One study (Salamon, 2017) showed that students who are physically active in muscle fitness tend to have a better memory. This means that being inactive causes students' memory to decrease.

In an article summarizing Jean Piaget's views on intellectual development, it was written that students should be active participants in the learning process. A teacher's job is to be a facilitator and give guidance to help students learn (Dudley & Goodyear, 2015; *Jean Piaget - intellectual development*, n.d.). A teacher's job is not to sit and lecture, not to sit and judge, but the teacher's job is to help the students learn from what they are applying. It is the teacher's job to help her students link the lesson to their real life and to make sure everyone is being guided to the objective. We cannot leave students learn without guidance. They might get lost, but at the same time we can't dictate everything and not let them experience things for themselves.

Teachers should have a balanced way of teaching. "A teacher can do so by letting their students be actively engaged in exploring, discovering, and reconstructing ideas, by letting them sometimes work together and sometimes individually, so a teacher briefly should use active learning and diverse activities" (McLeod, 2015, Educational Implications section, para. 7). So the teacher's job is to come to class

prepared with different types of activities to diverse activities and help students with different interests learn. “Bruner, however, proposes that learners’ construct their own knowledge and do this by organizing and categorizing information using a coding system. Bruner believed that the most effective way to develop a coding system is to discover it rather than being told it by the teacher” (McLeod, 2012, Educational Implications section, para. 5). So a teacher will help the students the most if she is a facilitator, not a dictator. When she guides them while they are working using their own hands in applying the coding system in their brain will decode and they will understand rather than memorize. Hands-on activities are important for students as we said because such activities help students learn. “Children are more likely to develop skills when they are having fun, but also when the skills have meaning for them; hands-on learning aims to provide for both of these characteristics of learning (Moyses, 2012, para.2).

As said before active learning helps students learn more. One study showed that “34% of students failed their course under traditional lecturing, compared to 22% of students under active learning” (Bhatia, 2014, May 12, para. 7). This shows that active learning improves students’ ability to learn and decreases failure.

As we can see in Figure 2 below, when the amount of lecture increased, the number of failed students increased. In addition, when active learning was used more, the number of failed students decreased. This figure also shows that about 20% of students failed when the teacher used active learning but about 30% of students failed when the teacher used lecture only.

Figure 2. Active learning vs. lecture and student failure.

Note: Adapted from Eddy, S., Freeman, S., Jordt H., McDonough, M., Okoroafor, N., Smith, M., & Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). *Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics*. Retrieved from <http://www.pnas.org/content/111/23/8410.full>

As a conclusion, teachers are facilitators while working on active learning. They guide the students to work on their own and to learn by experiencing, applying, and working on what is being taught using all their senses not only listening. When students use their senses, relate to real life experiences, and teachers guide them they will reach to the objective that should be learnt. Rather than students sitting and learning, teachers guide them to explore what should be learned actively this way students will be able to learn more.

Materials

To do active learning types of activities, facilities are needed and are important. But why are these facilities and hands-on activities important? Because they motivate the student to learn, and when our students are motivated to learn they will grasp more of the information given to them and they will last in their brains for a longer time.

Teaching materials come in different sizes and shapes and forms, but all of them have a common goal, which is improving student learning. Different governments of different countries believe in the importance of resources and manipulatives in classes to improve teaching. “The power of the learning environment to influence and promote learning is significant and the learning spaces and learning resources provide important opportunities for students to explore ideas and knowledge, collaborate, solve problems and develop knowledge and skills” (Abu Dhabi Education Council, 2013, para. 1).

Since materials in schools in general are beneficial, school boards have to make sure to invest sufficiently in appropriate learning materials for their schools. In the next section, I will discuss manipulatives and facilities separately, though they have the same outcome, which is improving student learning.

Manipulatives

“Teaching materials can support student learning and increase student success” (Ministry of Education, Guyana, 2016). If we take math for example, when we use manipulatives or different types of hands-on activities, this will make it easier for our students to learn successfully. “Research from both learning theory and classroom studies shows that using manipulatives to help teach math can positively affect student learning. This is true for students at all levels and of all abilities” (Research on Benefits of Manipulatives, n.d., Summary section, para.1). So the use of manipulatives in math is really important to help student understand abstract questions. However,

manipulatives are also important in Science, English and other subjects. They help students learn what is being taught and bringing textbooks to life (e.g., Berk, n.d.; “Reading Manipulatives,” n.d.). So the use of manipulatives is not important for one subject only, but for all subjects for students to learn better.

It is vitally important that in using manipulatives with children we focus on the notion that these tools will only be useful to our learners in their quest to become mathematicians to the extent that we allow them to use the manipulatives to make sense of mathematics and draw their attention to how they do so. (Back, 2013, para. 22)

When we give our students the time to think and apply what they are learning in a way they can link it to their real life, students will be able to surprise us by how much they can learn and give.

Those students who were taught using a differentiated curriculum that supplemented the textbook curriculum and were placed in various groups according to their performance level demonstrated significantly higher achievement on the post-test than did high-performing students who were taught using the textbook curriculum and whole-class instruction. (Huebner, 2010, what we know section, para. 4)

There are several types of active learning that teachers could implement in their classes to make it a lively classroom. Group work is one of them and is a helpful one because it helps our students learn how to work cooperatively, it helps the weak learn from the advanced, and the advanced will learn how to help, while in the process, clarifying and strengthening their own learning. Any other activity in class could be helpful, such as lectures, or videos—anything that can show the students different ideas, and different ways of learning something. This way the teacher will be able to

reach all her students and make sure they are learning in a nice way. To do all these activities schools should have some manipulatives for teachers to use and students to work on.

A study about how to teach actively and how teachers should help their student in working cooperatively in active learning activities, showed that

Instructors should continue to use team teaching when possible. If they are unable to do so, perhaps bring in guest lecturers or video clips that provide a different perspective. Active learning activities should continue to be used frequently. Instructors should be aware of the activities to make sure they are not seen as too childish. Students really enjoyed having an interactive interesting classroom. More importantly, they felt they really learned from it.

(Lauren, 2009, p. 60)

Another finding by Weber (2015) showed that

The combination of the active learning activities and the learning environment of the classroom (with student-choice seating and floor activities) led me to discover the power of group work. I instantly noticed a great change in the way students were completing assessments—they were excited to work together, they put forth more effort, they took on responsibility in splitting and organizing the tasks according each individual's strengths and interests, and they were proud and excited to share the final result. (p. 71)

The previous quotes show that active learning has a positive impact on students in many areas: learning, engagement, and how they see themselves. To be able to implement all these active learning activities schools should offer some manipulatives to be used. Active learning is not abstract: it is the school's job to find and get manipulatives to be used in hands-on activities.

In this section, we have seen that active learning is important for students because it helps them feel engaged and enjoy learning. Moreover, Active learning is helpful for teachers as well. To be able to do active learning and hands-on activities teachers need facilities and manipulatives. When you have good active learning activities and available materials this would enhance the students learning and teachers' way of teaching.

Facilities

A thesis done by Weber about hands-on activities showed that classroom teachers need facilities in their classes to be able to teach actively. But the problem is that not all schools have teaching facilities. (e.g., Spencer, 2012) There are many different reasons for this.

When the schools don't offer facilities for the teachers, and don't fund their schools wisely, the effectiveness of teaching and the level of education will decrease. One study (PennState, n.d.) found that school facilities help not only students but they also help teachers. Facilities improve outcomes for both students and teachers. The results showed that although "improving facilities comes at a financial cost, the benefits of such investments often surpass the initial fiscal costs. Policymakers, thus, should focus greater attention on the impacts of facilities and adopt a long-term cost-benefit perspective on efforts to improve school facilities" (PennState, n.d., Conclusion section, para. 1).

For one thing, "the percentage of the operating budget for the maintenance and management of school facilities has steadily decreased, creating a capital renewal crisis as a result of years of deferred maintenance at all levels of education" (Lackney & Picus, n.d., Facility management section, para. 2). In my opinion, this is a major problem because materials can make a major difference in students learning.

Facilities play a major role as much as manipulatives in our schools. The physical environment of the school also can effects students learning. Maslow's hierarchy of needs starts with the physiological need. If the lightning and the colors of the walls of the class are not relaxing for the students eyes the students will not be able to concentrate. If the school is not safe the student will not feel safe and will not be able to sit and listen to his teacher. This also affects the teachers' mood in the school. "Clearly, the teachers in buildings rated satisfactory view their classrooms more positively than do teachers in unsatisfactory buildings. These teachers view their classrooms as pleasant places in which to work and for students to learn" (Earthman & Lemasters, 2009, p. 333).

Good classes influence both teachers and students positively the teachers will teach better and the students will learn more.

A large body of research over the past century has consistently found that school facilities impact teaching and learning in profound ways. Yet state and local policymakers often overlook the impact facilities can play in improving outcomes for both teachers and students. While improving facilities comes at a financial cost, the benefits of such investments often surpass the initial fiscal costs. Policymakers, thus, should focus greater attention on the impacts of facilities and adopt a long-term cost-benefit perspective on efforts to improve school facilities. (The Importance of School Facilities in Improving Student Outcomes, n.d.)

Clearly, facilities are important, but a teacher can use different approaches of active learning such as grouping and pairing. Teachers can also use the talents of students to improve the whole class. For example, if a student is good in drawing,

he/she can decorate the classroom. In this way, teachers can improve students' skills outside of academic areas, and they will feel actively engaged.

So, as a conclusion we were able to see that even if it is going to cost the schools a bit more, it is worth it to get more and good facilities to make the teachers work easier and the students learning better. "Physical elements in the school environment can be shown to have discernible effects on teachers and learners. In particular, inadequate temperature control, lighting, air quality and acoustics have detrimental effects on concentration, mood, well-being, attendance and, ultimately, attainment" (Hall, Higgins, Wall, McCaughey, & Woolner, n.d., p. 36).

Here we have seen the importance of facilities and availability of materials in classes, and hands-on activities. Now we will see Montessori and the importance of real life experiences to students learning.

Methodologies

There are more than seven types of methodologies such as Montessori, Waldorf Reggio, Emilia High, Scope Bank, Street Parent, Co-Ops, PYP (Primary years program), and many more.

Different theorists have talked about the importance of facilities and good methodologies in teaching, in addition to different studies that have shown the same. The availability of materials makes certain kinds of teaching possible. Different methodologies also provide for active learning. Montessori and PYP are two of the methodologies that encourage and follow active learning. Once you help a preschooler enjoy learning, you will be able to show him that learning can be fun and easy therefore they will love to come to school and learn. How to do so? Easy... By using good methodologies, hands on activities, and having some helpful and enjoyable manipulatives you will be able to help your students learn while enjoying it.

Montessori Schools

One way of teaching is the Montessori philosophy. This school of thought believe that students should be actively engaged to learn better. This is a way of teaching that they follow:

Based on self-directed activity, hands-on learning and collaborative play. In Montessori classrooms children make creative choices in their learning, while the classroom and the teacher offer age-appropriate activities to guide the process. Children work in groups and individually to discover and explore knowledge of the world and to develop their maximum potential. (Montessori Northwest, 2015, para. 1)

So we can see that the Montessori schools believe and follow active learning. They help the students learn by doing things by themselves and their teachers are their guide or facilitator. Teacher gives them appropriate activities and they let their students explore alone or with their friends. I believe a teacher to do her job well and benefit the student she should be a facilitator while helping them explore.

Studies show that Montessori schools also help students think and work critically. Teachers should offer guided and age appropriate activities to help students think critically. In addition to that such schools must have safe places for outdoor activities to take students to (e.g., Montessori Northwest, 2015).

Montessori classes should be well equipped and decorated. Pictures should be hanged on the walls at the eye level of students not adults, those picture should be from real life. The class should have nice decoration to add interest to the room. Montessori schools should have enough spaces in their classes to help students develop their gross motor skills in addition to small and quite places for reading. In addition, Montessori schools care about outdoor activities and spaces as much as indoors.

The Montessori outdoor environment is prepared just as carefully as indoors. Since infants and toddlers are apt to put almost anything in their mouth, caregivers must survey the area regularly for any dangers. Outdoor areas require space for running, jumping, throwing, climbing, lying, sitting, balancing, watching, building, digging, playing with water, and exploring. It is not necessary to purchase expensive playground equipment for this age, though many Montessori outdoor spaces do have a sandbox. Ideally, there are a variety of hard and soft surfaces to meet the differing needs of children. (North American Montessori Center, 2007, para. 8).

Schools should offer their students a safe outdoor environment to help them explore. That is what Montessori schools are doing. By doing so I believe they are giving the chance to their students to explore the outer world not just virtually in class but also actively, and at the same time keeping them safe. We cannot just send our students outdoor to explore without making sure everything is safe. At the same time we need to send them to outdoor activities to learn better.

Some schools might care only about how the class is and if it is well equipped, whereas, Montessori schools do not care only about the inside but about the outside activities as well.

So Montessori schools care a lot about the physical aspect of the school.

Montessori classrooms are beautifully crafted environments designed to meet the needs of children in a specific age range. Dr. Maria Montessori discovered that experiential learning in this type of classroom led to a deeper understanding of language, mathematics, science, music, social interactions and much more.

Most Montessori classrooms are secular in nature, although the Montessori

educational method can be integrated successfully into a faith-based program (Montessori Northwest, 2015, section: What is Montessori, para. 1).

So as we saw before Montessori schools care about the outside activities as much as the inside. They want their students to be actively engaged in real life experiences outside class and to be able to learn music, math, science and different subjects inside class and still enjoying both.

The Montessori method, however, is mainly used in preschools. “The Montessori approach to education requires that children are placed in a well-planned and structured environment which will meet their individual educational and cultural needs. The children are free to follow their own interests within this planned environment, rather than being forced to learn something that is inappropriate to their developmental stage” (International Centre for Montessori Education, 2001, para 2). So what we can see is that the Montessori system gives the students the freedom to learn what they want to learn and in their own pace. The teacher is a facilitator for the students’ learning.

The principle of reality, not fantasy, in the classroom is one of the distinguishing features of a Montessori pre-school classroom. Montessori’s idea was to teach the children all about how to live in the real world and the Exercises of Practical Life are the first activities that provide these experiences. Children learn how to look after themselves and the environment as well as how to behave socially. (International Centre for Montessori education, 2001, Structured environment section, para. 9)

So Montessori schools work a lot on the physical environment of the school from inside and outside. They do so to help their students benefit in their social skills, real life experiences, academics, critical thinking and different aspects as well. They

don't let the students sit and listen but they help him explore and be actively engaged in different places to help him in different aspects and to develop properly.

Montessori schools make sure that their students are enjoying learning and not being over whelmed with it. That is why they allow their students to choose their own work rather than her giving them the job. It is more student-centered than teacher-centered. In addition, they believe that “an effective teacher in the Montessori classroom serves more as a guide, whose responsibility is to observe children during their periods and assess them according to mastery” (Grant, 2017, Montessori Classrooms section, para. 1). Teachers can easily be guides while the students are learning because teachers should have the ability to observe and know what motivates her students and be able to guide them easily.

Many studies were done on Montessori's theory that showed how such schools promote active learning and real life experiences for students. Moreover, this way of teaching affects students learning. A study done with two schools one that follows Montessori's method and another one that doesn't tested the students to see if one group had learned more. They found that

Both the Montessori and non-Montessori groups performed well on the STAAR but only the Montessori group performed well enough to meet the AYP [Adequate Yearly Progress] standards. The researcher also gave careful attention to the fact that Montessori students do not have the same advantages that non-Montessori students have in regards to being prepared for taking standardized assessments. (Salazar, 2013, p. 62)

However, there are not a lot of studies about Montessori, though it is well known. Studies are limited and not all of their findings were in favor of Montessori. “Though the studies on Montessori are limited and further complicated by the fact that

the name Montessori does not have a trademark, the method shows great potential for developing students who are problem-solvers, critical thinkers, and able to compete in the global economy” (Salazar, 2013, p. 65).

A teacher’s goal for students is not only to help them learn academics but also to help them become critical thinkers, and that is what Montessori schools are doing. So I believe that if a methodology is helping students develop skills it could be helpful to be used.

One study that had results that favor of Montessori found that “five-year-old Montessori pupils were better prepared for reading and math, and 12-year-olds wrote ‘significantly more creative’ essays using more sophisticated sentence structures”(Research shows benefits of Montessori education, 2006, para 3).

Montessori's methodology is helping students in being more creative because schools that follow that philosophy let their students do activities and use specific Montessori tools which is helping them more in their reading, math, and even communication skills. “Older Montessori pupils were more likely to choose “positive assertive responses” when dealing with unpleasant social situations, said the researchers” (Research shows benefits of Montessori education, 2006, para 16).

This shows that Montessori's philosophy helps young pupils in learning, and helps older pupils in dealing with life. This philosophy proves that it is not only helpful for kindergartens but for all students because it helps educationally and in social skills as well.

Another study also proved that Montessori's' way of teaching is good.

Among the five-year-olds, Montessori students proved to be significantly better prepared for elementary school in reading and mathematics than the non-Montessori children. They also tested better on ‘executive function,’ the ability

to adapt to changing and more complex problems, an indicator of future school and life success. (Highfield, 2006, para. 8)

Seeing this we can see that the Montessori approach is helpful for students and gives them good foundations for later education. So the Montessori approach in general might be a good education but is it so in all schools, ages, and all cultures? In addition, this study showed:

In social and behavioral measures, 12-year-old Montessori students were more likely to choose “positive assertive responses” for dealing with unpleasant social situations, such as having someone jump a queue. They also indicated a “greater sense of community” at school and felt that students helped, cared for and respected each other. (Highfield, 2006, para. 12).

In this second study we can see that the Montessori approach is also helpful for older students, not just kindergartens. But is it helpful in all countries and different cultures? That is what we will find out at the end of this research.

As this review has shown, the Montessori approach has been shown to have positive effects on students not just academically but also emotionally and socially. A teacher's job is to help students improve, grow, and learn as a whole, not only academically. When you work with students as a whole being you will be able to build good foundations for these students to become good, smart, thinkers and citizens of the future.

Table 1 shows the differences between the traditional approach of teaching and Montessori's methods. We can see in Table 1 how Montessori not only works on the social development of the child but also the cognitive, and this approach helps the student gain self-discipline rather than forcing it.

Table 1

Comparison between Montessori and Traditional Teaching Approaches

Montessori Method	Traditional Approach
Emphasis on cognitive and social development	Emphasis on social development
Teacher has unobtrusive role in classroom	Teacher is center of classroom as “controller”
Environment and method encourage self-discipline	Teacher enforces discipline
Mainly individual instruction	Group and individual instruction
Mixed age grouping	Same age grouping
Grouping encourages children to teach and help each other	Most teaching done by teacher
Child chooses own work	Activities structured for child
Child works as long as he wishes on chosen project	Child generally allotted specific time for work
Child discovers own concepts from self-teaching materials	Child is guided to concepts by teacher
Child sets own learning pace	Instruction pace usually set by group
Child spots own errors from feedback on material	If work is corrected, errors usually pointed out by teacher
Child reinforces learning by repetition and feelings of success	Learning is reinforced externally by repetition and rewards
Organized program for learning care of self and environment (polishing shoes, cleaning the sink, etc.)	Less emphasis on self-care instruction
Child can work where he chooses (yet not disturb work of others); group work is also encouraged	Child usually assigned own chair; encouraged to participate, sit still and listen during group sessions

Note. From *Montessori Unlimited*. (2017). Retrieved from <https://www.montessori.com/>

Montessori encourages mixed-age groups rather than same-age groups which will help students deal with different aged people and the grouping will improve students way of communicating and working in teams. In addition, each student has his own learning pace so in Montessori schools students will not feel the pressure to finish a certain objective in a specific time, the student will learn it in his own pace. Students can also discover the objectives rather than taking them through a lecture from a teacher. So in general the table below shows us how Montessori schools work actively with their students to help them develop properly different aspects in themselves.

“Montessori curriculum emphasizes learning as a process that cannot be determined by a child's age. Instead, learning is a process that is determined by the rate and speed at which a child can acquire one skill before moving on to another skill” (Grant, 2017, Foundations of Montessori Curriculum section, para. 2). This means that they make sure that students are learning and achieving what they intend to teach them. Even if students differ in the pace of learning in Montessori they make sure that no student is left behind.

The Lebanese Curriculum

As the teacher is a facilitator for students to learn, the curriculum should be a facilitator or a guide for teachers to know what to teach and how. Each country have their own school of thought about how they want to educate their students and in this part we will see how the Lebanese government thinks their students should be educated. In addition, the Lebanese curriculum has a little to say about what students will be learning academically. The academic curriculum starts in Grade 1. In preschool we will see themes that should be covered about real life experiences.

The Lebanese curriculum (Republic of Lebanon, 1997) states that our students are very precious. We should offer our students a safe environment with the freedom of speech. When they feel safe and free to talk and communicate we will be able to see what they have and how they think. By doing so, we will offer our students good foundations for their future. Childhood is the basic step to form a good student with good social and personal skills and characteristics. So what teachers teach in preschool will affect the students' future. The goal is to help our students as a whole body not just academics.

The Lebanese curriculum is divided into two ways: the longitudinal and the horizontal/ circular. The longitudinal is when teachers work with the students' development socially, physically, and academically. The horizontal is more about family and country/society. By following these two approaches, students will be able to build their intrapersonal and interpersonal identity in an ideal way and as a whole.

It is our job to teach students think critically and alone because if we don't help them do so they will not be able to shine in the future and be independent citizens. In addition, our students should use their senses to learn, by playing, touching, and communicating with people surrounding them.

Most importantly the curriculum (Republic of Lebanon, 1997) shows that teachers should encourage their students to participate and answer, the more you encourage the more the students will give because they will feel safe and not threatened to answer. Each student is unique and has his own pace in learning and own way. We should always respect and keep in mind this point to be able to reach all.

Preschool is the first step in the whole ladder students climbs. Students first social encounter is with the parents then when they go to school teachers job is to help

their students to leave their comfort zone and family to start meeting and practicing their social skills and being dependable.

In that stage teachers should show their students care and love for the students' benefit. Families and schools should work together in that stage to build a bridge for them from their homes to the real life. However, the Lebanese curriculum does not tell the schools clearly what students should know at the end of KG3; it just gives them themes (see Table 2) to teach, and it is up to the school system what they want their student to know at the end of KG3. I believe that it would have been helpful if the Lebanese curriculum had given some rubrics about what students should know before they enter to Grade 1 so that all schools will offer same level of education and be fair to all students everywhere.

Table 2

المحتوى من منهج الروضة الثانية (Themes Studied by KG3)

الروضة الثانية	
المحور الأول: الناس ومجتمعهم	المحور الثاني: البيئة الطبيعية
1- الناس	9- النباتات
2- الأسرة	10- الحيوانات
3- الغذاء	11- الصخور
4- المهن	12- الهواء
5- المواصلات	13- الماء
6- وسائل الاتصال	
7- الآلات	
8- المناسبات والأعياد	

Note: Adapted from Republic of Lebanon. (1997). منهج مرحلة الروضة. [Preschool Curriculum]. Retrieved from <http://www.crdp.org/curr-content-desc?id=25>

In Table 2 you can see the themes that the Lebanese government has put in the curriculum, and you can see that it is about social topics such as families, transportations, animals, jobs, etc. These are important, but they have nothing to do with English and math which I believe are concepts that are missing.

Table 2 shows what concepts the Lebanese curriculum expects us to teach in preschool. However, it doesn't show what we should teach in subjects such as Math, English, or French that schools teach. The schools are free to choose what they want their students to be able to know as foundations in the kindergarten classes to be ready for the Grade 1 Lebanese curriculum. They can divide their ideas over the first three years of schooling in any way they wish. In addition, it's up to the school to choose how to teach and what is the best way to help their students learn.

In this chapter we have seen the importance of active learning and how it improves students learning. In addition, to the importance of the use of facilities and manipulatives while doing active learning. We have also seen the Montessori way of teaching and how it follows active learning and help students learn, At last we saw how the Lebanese curriculum have some themes that are helpful but how is has no guidelines to what preschools should be teaching in academics.

CHAPTER 3

METHODS

In this thesis I was trying to find out if different methodologies have different effects on KG3 student learning in preschool, and whether different materials and facilities are important in helping students learn more. The design of the study is cross-sectional. The method that this study will follow is a mixed method, both quantitative and qualitative. First there was a descriptive, qualitative and quantitative observation to determine the methods used in two different schools: one using Montessori, and the second, a school that is just a regular preschool, with no particular method given. I also used a checklist that included some points about the facilities that are available and some points about the environment of the school to determine the materials and facilities available in the two different schools. Second, there was a brief survey of parents to ensure that both schools have similar demographics, and to gather some demographic information about the students' families. Last but not least was the end of year assessments to see if there is any difference in student learning between the two approaches.

Population and Sample

In this study I worked with two different schools that have the same demographics but use different methodologies and have different facilities. The study will be done only on KG3 students. One school has four sections of KG3 and each class has approximately 20 students. I worked with one section and a half in that school to

have 27 students. The second school has five sections of KG3 with about 30 students each. I worked with one section from this school. In total, I tested about 56 students in two different schools.

Instruments

Classroom Observation

In order to assess the methods followed in the two schools, I will use a qualitative instrument that will help me see how those two schools teach. What system do they follow? Appendix A shows the rubric that I will use to assist in my qualitative observation. It is taken from a *Classroom Observation Form* (n.d.) which I found online. This form helped me observe the subject matter they teach, how they organize the class, teaching methods, presentations, assistance for students, and so on. This way I was able to compare the differences in both schools regarding the two different methods and how they compare. While observing I took notes of what was going on in the class; I did not just fill out the observation sheet. I observed in the two schools for a total of 8 hours each to see how they teach and what materials they use while teaching.

Facilities and Materials Availability Checklist

In order to assess the materials available in the two schools, I used a quantitative instrument called *The Facilities Checklist* (see Appendix B), which is something I have created to fit the needs of my study. I made this on my own after reading about the important facilities that should be available in classes and what sorts of facilities could help teachers in teaching. After checking different articles and ideas about lists of facilities that are important for a KG3 classroom I was able to make the checklist to use while observing. I used some of the common ideas I found in several articles such as study centers, play areas, libraries, and some additional ideas that I saw are important

for teaching. This helped me observe and see what different facilities both schools have and what they do not have. Facilities observed include items such as LCDs, a photocopier machine, educational toys, learning centers, books, or any other facility that might help improve student learning.

Demographics Survey

A short researcher-developed demographic survey was sent to parents of the students in both schools to make sure that the students are from the same socioeconomic status—to ensure that the groups of students are equivalent. Appendix C shows the survey which I created to fill this need. It included about 10 questions that helped us know if the parents are educated and can help their children or not. In addition, it helped us know the average of the income of the families to make sure they are all offered the manipulatives, and facilities that improve learning and increase knowledge.

End-of-Year Achievement Test

At the end of the year, a developmental test was done to all the KG3 students in both schools to see if the availability of facilities, hands-on activities, and different methodologies makes any changes in student learning. To assess learning, I used the *Primary Assessment*, by Calverton Education (2013), which is a test of readiness for Grade 1. Some of the questions are about reading words, others about continuing a sequence of a story, others are about putting missing letters, and some rhyming words. I slightly adapted this instrument by deleting some of the words that might be okay for American students, but Lebanese students might not know. In addition, I added some questions that would show the general knowledge of the students and some memory questions. For the complete instrument, see Appendix D.

In Table 3 below you can see the instruments' internal consistency. It shows that the alpha reliability of the instrument is sufficient.

Table 3

Alpha Reliability

Section	Coefficient
Memory	0.287
Reading	0.601
General knowledge	0.508
Prediction	0.834

Ethical Precautions

There is no harm in the study I am doing for anyone: not students nor the school. Names will not be required so the answers are confidential. In addition, the data collection is limited to only what is needed. Students have the freedom to withdraw at any time without penalty. The names of the two schools will not be used in any of the discussion, in order to protect them from any potential harm.

Procedures and Analysis

In this thesis, compare not only academics but also creativity and logical thinking since the Lebanese curriculum believe that preschool goals are not only academics. There are some limitations, one of which is that facilities and methodologies are both being studied together and not separately, while on the contrary, I believe they are not separate topics and they can work parallel to each other.

I started my study by attending two different schools and observing how the environment, school building, decorations, and so on, look like. So after I did my study

and before I start stating the facts that I found I will start by talking briefly about the appearances of both schools and comparing between them after I have entered the classes in both schools and observed the methods that are being followed, and the facilities available and being used.

After I gather the information needed I will use the *T*-test to compare between both schools regarding the facilities and the methodologies. In addition, I will be sending a Demographics Survey to the students' parents in the classes I am observing. This will allow me to deduce that both schools have students from the same demographics.

At the end of the year I will perform an achievement test to the students that I have been observing and I will use the grades deduced to compare them using ANOVA. The last step accordingly will be using the facilities checklist results and the outcomes of the end of year test to complete a correlation comparison and assess whether the facilities had any effect on students outcomes. By following all those steps I was able to find out whether different methods and good use of facilities affect students' learning.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS

In this section we will be seeing the results of the classroom observations of the two schools. These will be descriptive. After that, we will see how the two schools are similar or different in the availability of facilities and in the physical environment. In addition, we will see if both schools have the same demographics, so that we can draw similar conclusions about the role of methodologies and facilities in student learning. And last, we will see the test scores of students in both schools and whether there are differences between them, or similarities, and we will try to determine why.

Classroom Observation

I did observations in two schools: one that follows Montessori, and one that does not. That way we will be able to see how the schools methodologies are different, how the everyday routine is different, and how the physical environment differs in both schools. Since both schools follow different approaches, the class sessions should be different and the school environments should be different to serve the way of teaching. The two observations are described and analyzed below.

Description of the Montessori School

Outside the class. The Montessori school that I observed has seven buildings and one of them is for preschool where Montessori approaches are followed. When you enter the building you can see stairs at the right that lead you to the teachers' room and the administration office. In front of you there is a big, covered playground with slides and other toys for the kids to play with during recess time. To the left you can see a big

room with several hallways and doors and stairs leading downstairs. In this big room you can see big, lovely finger print paintings done by the kids in the art classes throughout the previous years. To the right you can see stairs that lead you to KG2 and KG1 classes, and in this same floor there are the KG3 classes. Each hallway has 2 or 3 classrooms. The walls of these hallways are white and have paintings hanging on them, which make them colorful and cheerful. As the literature shows (e.g., Lizardi, n.d.; Edwards, 2006), the environment of the school helps the students in learning. If the school has bad painted walls and broken desks the students will not feel motivated to study in that place, whereas, if the walls are colorful and the hallways are decorated that will improve students motivation to learn. In short, the environment and the physical surroundings of this school are attractive and interesting. This shows that this school has worked on the physical environment of the school to make it a better, motivating, and safe place for students to learn and be in.

Inside the classroom. When you enter any of the classrooms, you will see that each of them has a small path that leads to a room inside the classroom for the students to put their bags, bottles, and jackets in. In the KG3 classrooms where I observed, the tables are arranged in rows or half a square, all facing the board—not in circles like KG1 and KG2. On the side of one of the walls, you can see shelves where the students put their books, pencils and pen holders. On another wall you can see shelves where they have Montessori toys. On the third and fourth wall you can see boards, and under the boards in the corner there are 3 separate desks. This is so that when a student needs extra help, the assistant can sit with him/her alone to help them. On the fourth wall there is the teacher's desk with shelves behind it where she puts all the manipulatives such as scissors, pens, and erasers. Above all of the shelves in the classroom, you can

see bulletin boards with decorations, words they are studying, letters of the alphabet, rules, and a calendar.

The classroom is decorated nicely and is very colorful so the students will enjoy their stay in the class. There is a big carpet under the desks and a space in front of the desks for the students to sit on the carpet from time to time. They have tables in the corners to help slower students since Montessori, as we read before, works with each student at his/her own pace. For that reason, they have these tables for the assistant to sit with the slower students and help them grasp the concepts they should learn.

Montessori manipulatives. These Montessori toys are not just any toys, but specific manipulables that have academic, motor skill, and critical thinking purposes. For example, they have toys with numbers that help the students count. They have a group of pictures where they have to find the intruder among these pictures (which one doesn't belong?). They also have a box that has cubes. They have to put the cubes in the same color order to match the picture on the top of the box. They even have another toy with different shapes with small holes in the middle of them. These shapes are to be placed on a wooden base that has metal posts coming out of it. This helps the students with their sensory-motor skills, because they have to concentrate on how to put the shapes onto the metal bars, and they also have to sort them so that each shape is placed onto one single post. Students can also use these shapes to make patterns in math—not just sorting—and for some other learning activities. Montessori teachers care a lot about the sensory-motor skills of the students. They teach them to hold everything in both hands and walk. They also might give them a bottle and water to put in cups, or even soap and water to clean their shoes. They try to work with them not only on academics, but on sensory-motor skills, critical thinking, and other skills that can help them in everyday life.

In every class there are about thirty students with one teacher and one assistant who stays with the teacher the whole time to help her. All the teachers teaching have done training in how to apply Montessori methods in the classroom. They try to use pictures, objects, songs, stories and different activities to make the class vivid and give examples for the students that they can connect to.

In one of the classes that I observed I saw real photographs hanging on the board that they used the previous day in their lesson. In addition, the teacher concentrated a lot on the idea that while sitting and studying, hands should be on the lap. They should not be moving, whereas, when they have an activity, they can move.

Ways of teaching. In KG1 and KG2 they follow the Montessori philosophy the whole time, more than KG3. They have a lot of activities. For example, if they are learning about baking cakes, they bake a cake. If they are learning about ironing, they have a toy iron and clothes, and they use them. In addition, they have a toy house they use it to learn the different parts of the house. All of the learning objectives are learnt in hands-on activities from real life situations. They also have educational toys, each toy with a purpose. Some are for critical thinking; others for math or English.

Each child can take a rug put it on the carpet and put the toy he wants on it and sit and play with it. Toys should not be all over the carpet, just on their rug. That way, each student will learn his limits, and the concept of personal space. Before using any toy, or teachers giving the students the toy, the teacher gives them a lecture about it, explaining how it is used and its purpose. That way, when the students take the toys they know how to play. Teachers just pass between them—they do not interrupt the students or do things for them.

During my observation, they started their English period by reviewing the sounds of the letters and then the teacher played a song that had all the names and sounds of the letters included in it. While listening to it, each letter had its own action where the teacher and students were doing them to help them memorize it. After saying the sounds by pointing to the letters hanging over the board, they started doing actions, and after that they started singing. At the end, they related some of the words to real life words. One of the examples was *exit*. They wrote *exit* over the door to see how to exit a room.

When they started studying about vowels, the teacher put on the board a drawing of a cupcake, a bone, and different real life things that have the sounds of long and short vowels in them. Those images had ribbons going down from them, and every time a student gave a word with the same vowel as in the drawing, they would stick the word on its ribbon. These items were then used for the purpose of teaching long and short vowels. The teacher took time to give examples, to sing songs, and do actions with the students. They used differentiated activities in order to make the concept clear. The whole time they were sitting straight on their chairs for about 30 minutes.

When the students got tired of sitting, listening, and singing, they started moving. The teacher had an already-prepared list of words to give to every student. But before handing it to each student, each one in his turn read a word from the list that she wrote on the board. When they finished, she gave them the list to read silently. Then when they finished, they raised their hands so she could give them scissors to cut out the words. At the end, they had to put the words over each other and to put a paper clip on them so that the words would look like a booklet. Then they could take the booklets they have made home with them to read them rather than taking a regular reading list.

When the students finished with the reading activity, the teacher asked them to sit on the carpet in front of the desks and they did the calendar, using full sentences, reviewing today's date, yesterday's and tomorrow's. They sang a song for March, a song for the 12 months, a song for the 7 days and one for the four seasons. They have a CD player in class that they used to hear one of the songs on.

After the calendar session, the teacher read a story for them while she was sitting on a low chair and they were on the carpet next to her, and she showed them the pictures in the story. Before reading, she asked them what they think the story was going to be about. While reading the story, she demonstrated parts of it to show how things really happened. Then the teacher wrote the sentences of the story on the board and the students started reading the story and practicing. At the end, she did a game that girls would read alone then boys alone, to see who would win. When they had a tie score, she asked them to read all together: if one boy didn't read, all the boys would lose, and same thing for the girls. In this way, she gave them the responsibility to read so that they won't lose and they all started reading excitedly. That was one of the classes.

Other classes also followed, with the same way of teaching. They used different teaching aids to make the class vivid, such as pictures, real live objects, songs, crafts, and games. All classes have the same rules and regulations for class management. One of the things is that they have to sit straight with their hands on their laps when the teacher is talking and they must not yell out the answers. They have to raise their hands and follow the classroom rules. Another rule is that each teacher has a triangle, and when she rings it, all the students should stop talking and look at her.

The classrooms are decorated with what they will study or what they already studied to be able to use these items for revision later on. The classes were going on

smoothly, teachers ready to teach and having everything they need prepared next to them so that when it is time to use them, they do not have to go and search for things. Respect was mutual between teachers and students. Students were required to listen and not talk while the teacher was talking and she listened to them when they talked. She also called them her ladies and gentlemen and asked them to behave as such.

In my opinion, using different teaching aids in the classroom is really important. I liked how the teachers related the lessons to real life experiences. Teaching was going very well, students were interactive, and the class was enjoyable. However, I think they could have added more of the hands-on activities or could have asked the students to go up to the board and talk. In my opinion, leaving KG3 students sitting reading and seeing pictures and singing without moving around for 30 to 45 minutes is too much. As a KG3 teacher I believe that differentiating activities should be done throughout the lesson, not only using lecturing and then giving time to use the manipulatives. A teacher should try to teach the lesson using those fun manipulatives to reach the students faster and in a better way.

Description of the Non-Montessori School

Outside the class. In this school, as you enter, there is one floor for all Kindergarten students. There are 12 sections and all are on the same floor. The walls in the halls are colored and so are the walls of the classrooms. Some are yellow; others are blue or green. The tables are put in circles in the classroom and each table is a different color. In the hallways you can see flowers hanging down from the ceiling and decorated bulletin boards. In the classrooms, you can see decorated bulletin boards as well as words or sentences between the flowers that students read every day with their teachers.

Inside the class. Each student has his own shelf which contains his books and pencil case. The class has centers. One side of the room has the shelves; the other is the toys and games center, computer center, reading center. KG1, KG2, and KG3 have the same centers, and the classes look the same, however, the way teachers teach and what they teach differs.

Classroom manipulatives. The toys in the classroom are not Montessori toys: they have blocks, puzzles, letters and strings, magnetic letters, and so on. They play with them every morning for 30 min. Some are educational and some are not.

There are some classroom rules that students follow, and they are hung on a board. They read them every day. They also play a game that their chair is the home, their finger is the key, they can't move out of their chairs without using their finger and putting it up. When they finish they have time to read quietly till their friends finish their work as well. When all are done, they sit back on the carpet to start something new. The teacher uses things like pictures, videos, or artwork to explain each lesson.

Ways of teaching. Since this school is not a Montessori school, they don't have Montessori toys in KG1 and in KG2 for students to work with. In addition, in this school students in KG1 learn colors and numbers, and then they start applying the concepts using worksheets. They have few activities for them to understand the lessons more. The teacher explains with an activity then shows the students how to do the paper in front of them. Then she asks them to go to their places and apply the learning on the paper the same way she did. She keeps her example on the board for students to look at when they feel stuck.

In KG1 in the non-Montessori school I found that they did few activities, few work sheets, and not much painting or cutting. They did some differentiated activities to help the students not only educationally but also with their sensory-motor skills.

However, in KG2 they have more work sheets than KG1 and when the teacher demonstrates how to do the paper on the board, she removes it when it is their turn to work. In this way she is able to see who got the concept and who didn't. The teacher works with groups, not the whole class together. While she works with one group, the others are watching or doing some art work to keep them busy because in this school the teacher is alone in the class. She has no assistant with her: the assistants only help in the artwork and filing but they don't stay in the classroom.

In KG3 classes the teacher gives them 30 minutes to play in the morning while waiting for all the students to arrive. At 8 in the morning the class starts with the circle time first. All the students together say what the date was yesterday, using full sentences. Then the teacher says who the line leader is, and asks for him to stand and say the date using a full sentence. This activity helps students read words (day, month, season), helps them talk in public and helps students in communication skills. After they finish they recite a poem everyday all together, for the student to memorize it. The teacher says it after she explains it and they repeat after her. They repeat it every day till they memorize it. This activity helps the students to use their memory. When they finish, the class starts. The teacher turns on the projector and the computer and they hear a story about the letter they are studying, listen to a song, read some words, and do activities/games on the computer such as putting letter properly to form a word or dividing words between real words and silly words. When they finish with the group work, the teacher explains what they have to do in their books, and they go to their places to work on their own.

When the reading is done, the teacher takes the book and gives them instructions as to what they are supposed to do next, but without her solving the problems in front of them. She wants them to solve what they know on their own. They

all go to their places and do the pages they are expected to do and come one by one or stand in a line by the teacher's desk for her to correct what they did and explain if they did it wrong. This way students will feel independent and responsible. Rather than copying the teachers work, they have to think and solve the problems on their own.

When they start learning math, they do not use the computer to explain.

However, the teacher does use blocks to teach patters and addition, they use sand to practice writing letters, and they use flashcards to practice addition. They use different aids and activities to learn new concepts. The teacher solves the questions with them on the board then erases them. Afterwards, they have to do the work, because the concepts are new. But later on, when she feels the students are capable of doing them alone she reviews with them. This time, the concept is done with different numbers or different questions and then she asks them to go and solve them on their own.

When they finish all the school work and the objectives that the teacher has for them for the day, they sit and take a book to try to read while their friends finish their work or sometimes the teacher gives them extra work to practice more. When they all finish and the teacher is done with what she has for them they sit all together on the carpet including the teacher and read a story all together. This will help them read and see a few words they studied, and helps them with conversations. It also calms them down till the parents come and pick them up. So in this school there is a lot of differentiation in the activities that they do: some are usual worksheets, but they also have songs, videos or applying concepts using toys. All of this variety helps the students learn each in his own way, and this is really important to make sure that everyone gets the chance to learn in his own way (e.g. Raffaelli, 2014).

Montessori vs. Non-Montessori School

The two schools I observed were similar in many respects, yet they differed in important ways. In the Montessori school they actually spend most of the time with KG1 and KG2 student doing activities for the students to learn how to work with the Montessori equipment. In KG2 they start doing a few written assignments. However, in the Non-Montessori school the students are starting to do worksheets starting from KG1 with some activities in class.

Both schools have toys, but the kind of toys differ. Some of the toys they use are educational, while some are not. The toys in the Montessori schools mostly help with sensory-motor skills, others with thinking. Some are educational, and some are items that are from real life that can help them in everyday living. In the non-Montessori school they have some toys that are educational but others that are not. That is, not all the toys in the non-Montessori school are educational. When you enter to a Montessori class you see it all full with toys. Some are standardized, like the wooden blocks that can be ordered from longest to shortest or from thicker to thinner. There are many colorful toys that can help in critical thinking sorting, or even patterns and shapes that can help with math or sensory-motor skills. There are also puzzles to help critical thinking, and toy objects like we use in the real life to practice real-life experiences—all of these for the sake of teaching. When you enter the non-Montessori class you see just a few toys, such as small blocks, two or three puzzles, magnetic letters, or words and laminated pictures that students play with while a teacher and a student and read together.

The teacher in the non-Montessori school has access to a computer with internet and a projector in class to facilitate when she is teaching. The Montessori school does not. Both schools use active learning in their own way. However, Montessori schools

have some outside space for outdoor activities to be visited and used, whereas, the non-Montessori school does not have this advantage.

In addition to all that, I loved how the Montessori school trains their students in motor skills even while playing—how they ask them to hold a bottle in both hands while walking, how they teach them the concept of space, such that each student takes a mat and puts the toys on it and can't go out of that space. These points Montessori work on but the non-Montessori school does not.

While reading stories Montessori students were engaged and started reading with the teacher whereas, in the non-Montessori school, when the teacher read a story for them, some were not interested and didn't pay attention. In addition, while the teachers were reading the story, the Montessori students were able to read a big part from the story for themselves—more than the students in the non-Montessori school.

It was the same with the outdoor activities, the fieldtrips, exploration, and the educational toys. The Montessori students were able to learn to read, engage and enjoy it more than the non-Montessori school. This was what I saw during the observations. Both schools have students with good reading skills but the Montessori students were better since they read more and were engaged more.

Comparison of Facilities and Environment in Both Schools

After entering and observing in the school and having some help from the coordinator, I was able to fill out the checklist regarding the facilities available in each school and about the environment of the school (see Appendix B). On the checklist, 0 meant Not Available, 1 meant Inadequate, 2 meant Adequate, and 3 meant Super Adequate.

Facilities

The facilities in the two schools were similar but had notable differences. Table 4 below shows that in the non-Montessori school, the students don't have access to computers, whereas, the Montessori students have access. Computers are adequate for teachers' use in both schools. In both schools the teachers' room had computers that teachers can use. However, teachers had few computers—not enough—only three computers for about 30 teachers.

Both school have super adequate photocopy machines. The printing services are adequate in the Montessori school but super adequate in the non-Montessori school. This difference may be because the Montessori school doesn't focus as much on worksheets and things that need printing.

The non-Montessori school has adequate multimedia centers because they have computers, projectors and I-Pads in class whereas, the Montessori school doesn't. The non-Montessori school has a TV set and a projector in class, whereas the Montessori school doesn't. By this we can see that the non-Montessori school can offer students the ability to watch videos and see the things they are studying virtually whereas, the non-Montessori can only show their students pictures. This gives a good advantage to the non-Montessori school because teachers have the chance to show their students different things regarding the lesson which will help the students learn, explore and enjoy the lesson more.

The Montessori school got super adequate scores for teacher assistants in the classroom, whereas the non-Montessori school does not have classroom assistants. The teacher in the non-Montessori school has all the load to manage: teaching, and doing activities on her own, whereas the Montessori school teachers have the chance to share the job and work with students at a more personal level. This point is in favor of the

Montessori school because students have the chance to sit one-on-one with the teacher, or with a small group that needs extra help, because she has someone to work with the other students. The non-Montessori school teachers cannot always do so.

Both schools have excellent teacher desks, which are big and full of facilities and colorful books that teachers can use for the lessons. In addition, both schools have educational toys but the non-Montessori school has only an adequate number of educational toys, whereas, the Montessori school has many more. In the Montessori school you can see a lot of wooden toys, puzzles, toys from the activities of real life, shapes, blocks, and long sticks. All these are to help students use their critical thinking and learn new concepts in their studies and from real life. The non-Montessori school has toys which are colorful, but not all of them are for a purpose. Some are just for fun.

In general the totals in Table 4 regarding facilities show that both schools got an average of about 2. This means both schools have an adequate number of facilities that can be used in class, but there are interesting patterns of differences, with the Montessori school emphasizing computers for students and support for teachers, and the non-Montessori emphasizing TV and projection and multimedia centers. It is difficult to say that one set of priorities is better than the other, but it is clear that no school can provide everything, and choices have to be made as to what items are a priority.

We can see that there are no big differences between both schools in the availability of materials. Some items are found in one school and some are not, but in general both schools have good facilities for active learning. However, one school which is the Montessori school has more educational toys than the other that could help its students learn more, faster, and in a fun way. In addition the Montessori school has two teachers in class which could be an advantage to the school, teacher and students.

Table 4

Availability of Facilities in the Schools

Facilities	Montessori	Non-Montessori
Students have access to computers.	3	0
Computers are available for teachers use.	2	2
Availability of printing service.	2	3
Availability of photocopier machine in the school.	3	3
Availability of a TV set to be used for educational purposes.	0	3
Availability of a functional projector for educational purposes.	0	3
Availability of a teacher assistant always in class.	3	0
Availability of educational toys (More than 10 in each class).	3	2
Is there a teacher's desk?	3	3
Availability of multimedia center.	0	2
Totals	1.9	2.1

This does not mean that the non-Montessori school is bad. The non-Montessori school has projectors, technologies that can be a facilitator for the teacher and the student. Non-Montessori schools have toys even if not Montessori toys but the teacher can benefit from them and relate them to the lesson in a way or another, such as using blocks for patterns or for sorting as I observed that she did. This is what I found about the availability of materials and manipulatives in the classes now we will be seeing the physical environment.

When we look at Table 5 we can see the differences in the two schools in the area of physical environment and space usage. Both schools have an adequate open area on the floor, play center, and outdoor places for students to visit for active learning. The Montessori school has super adequate storage units such as bookshelves, play areas, large playgrounds, music and dance rooms whereas, non-Montessori schools have adequate facilities, but not as nice. Both schools have super adequate places for students to place their belongings in. However, Montessori school has inadequate scores for using different learning centers in class, whereas, the non-Montessori does

better in this area. The Montessori school has a super adequate art room whereas, the non-Montessori school has no art room at all.

The Montessori school goes on fieldtrips adequately where as non-Montessori school has few fieldtrips, which the supervisor and I considered inadequate. The Montessori school has a super adequate, safe sports room, whereas the non-Montessori got inadequate for the big, safe sports room. The Montessori school has a big room where students can go run and explore; one part indoors and the other part of it outdoors, so they can explore different things. Since the Montessori site has a better space for students to explore, and they go on fieldtrips more than non-Montessori students, they would be exposed to more words, more activities, and information so they might become better readers and more knowledgeable in general information.

Table 5

Physical Environment of the Schools

Environment	Montessori	Non-Montessori
Is there an open area on the floor?	2	2
Is there a storage unit such as bookshelves?	3	2
The use of different centers in class	1	2
Availability of a play center	2	2
Quiet places to read.	3	0
Availability of play areas	3	2
A space for children to store their work and personal belongings	3	3
Availability of library services or a reading room.	3	0
Availability of places students can visit for active learning (outdoor activities)	2	2
Availability of different large playgrounds.	3	2
Availability of a music room.	3	2
Availability of a dance room.	3	2
Availability of an art room.	3	0
Availability of fieldtrips on lessons taught.	2	1
Availability of a big and safe sports room.	3	1
Total	2.6	1.5

The Montessori's school total was super adequate and the non-Montessori school total was adequate. Both have things in common but the Montessori school seems that it has more places for them to visit, and to go learn and do activities in. In addition, the Montessori school not only has spaces for outdoor activities but also takes students on fieldtrips for different lessons. The non-Montessori school has no outdoor spaces, nor do they go on fieldtrips.

In conclusion, we can see that there are differences between the two school environments as shown in Tables 4 and 5. But the reality on the ground is clearer than the tables show. In virtual resources, the Montessori school may have a slight disadvantage, but the real resources that they have available seem to more than make up for it. Both schools have positive things but they emphasize different goals. The question is whether these lead to different educational results.

Demographics Survey

Surveys were sent to parents in both schools to evaluate whether both schools had the same demographics. It would not be fair to compare the results of tests across the two schools if they are drawn from students in very different socioeconomic levels of the society. For this reason, parental data was included in the analysis.

In the Montessori school, the parents' degrees, the availability of books at home, and how much time they spend time with their child reviewing were significantly higher (see Table 6) than in the non-Montessori school.

Both groups had similar scores for the availability of electronics, internet, time spent playing at home with educational toys, and the overall income of the household. So four of the questions showed that there is no difference and three showed that there is. You can see the difference by numbers in Table 6 below regarding the first 6

questions. Regarding the availability of internet at home they all answered with a yes so I did not include it in the table. However, knowing that all students have internet access at home we will be able to conclude that they all have easy access to information and to general knowledge or any type of knowledge.

Table 6

Demographics in Both Schools

	Montessori	Non- Montessori	P-value
1. Highest degree	2.61	1.95	0.003*
2. Number of story books available for your child at home	2.94	2.70	0.054*
3. Own smartphone, I-Pad, Laptop	2.16	2.40	0.307
4. Time playing with educational toys?	2.50	2.60	0.548
5. Time spent reviewing what your child has done in school	2.72	2.35	0.021*
6. Overall income of the house	2.94	2.75	0.106

Test Scores Comparison

Table 7 below shows the mean memory ability scores from the test that was done. The first part of the test was testing memory where I put 11 objects on a table and students saw them and then I hid them. The students were then given papers with 19 pictures on them, and among them were the 11 objects they had seen. They had to circle what they saw on the table. The Montessori pupils scored an average of 15.9 out of 19 which means that the mean of the class was 15.9 which means the mean is 84%.

Few students got less than 15 correct answers and some got more than 15 over 19 correct. The mean score of the non-Montessori pupils was actually higher, at 16.8 out of 19 so the mean of the class was 88%. The t -test was used to determine if there was a significant difference between the two groups. The t -test result shows a p-value of 0.204, which means that there is no significant difference between the memory ability of the two groups. I think both school were able to get good grades on the memory section because I noticed that both schools work on improving the students' memory, each in their own way. The Montessori school had toys that helped the students memorize, whereas the non-Montessori school used poems and stories. This shows that both schools are doing well in this area.

There was no difference between the two schools in my opinion because both schools are working hard on improving students' memory, each in its own way. The non-Montessori school teaches poems and helps students memorize fun and nice poems, whereas, the Montessori school uses toys to help them memorize. Personally, I believe teachers can train their students memorize in different ways, and, as long as students memories are being trained, the results is good in both schools. It does not seem to matter how this training takes place.

Table 7

Memory Ability Mean Scores

School Type	Mean Score
Montessori	15.93
Non-Montessori	16.84

Table 8 below shows that the mean of reading ability score of Montessori pupils was 17.00 while the mean of reading ability score of non-Montessori pupils was 15.518. The *t*-test was used to determine if there is a significant difference between the two groups. The *t*-test shows a p-value of 0.0011. This is less than 0.05 which means that there is a significant difference between the ability of reading between both groups. Pupils in the Montessori school scored significantly higher and were able to read more than pupils in the non-Montessori school. This shows that the methodology of the Montessori school and how they teach letters and sounds in KG does make a difference compared to the non-Montessori school, because Montessori students were able to read better. Note that the difference was not large, but it was significant. From my observation, it was clear that the Montessori school had toys and books that could help students learn letters by using their fingers in tracing the letter in books or in the sand. By doing these things, students were given the opportunity to explore reading while using more than one sense—not just seeing, but also feeling. In my opinion this would help the information stick more in their brains. For this reason, I believe the Montessori students were able to read more.

Table 8

Sounds of Letter Reading Ability Mean Scores

School	Mean Score
Montessori	17.00
Not-Montessori	15.51

Table 9 below shows that the mean of the general knowledge of the students in the Montessori school is 5.41 while the mean of the general knowledge of the students in the non-Montessori school is 4.77. The *t*-test was used to determine if there is a significant difference between two groups. The *t*-test shows a p-value of 0.027. This is less than 0.05 which means that there is a significant difference in the general knowledge ability between the two groups. Pupils in the Montessori school scored significantly higher than pupils in the non-Montessori school.

Table 9

General Knowledge Ability Mean Scores

School	Mean Score
Montessori	5.41
Not-Montessori	4.77

I believe that students in the Montessori school might have more general knowledge because they do more outdoor activities and go on more fieldtrips than the students in the non-Montessori school. This also showed up in the checklist discussed earlier. Personally I believe that fieldtrips and outdoor activities put students in real life experiences about the themes they should study and they will understand them more and learn them faster. I agree with McLeod (2015) that active learning can be done by letting student construct, discover and reconstruct and by taking them out of school helping them explore we will be helping them to learn and gain more knowledge.

General knowledge can be gained in different ways. All students have internet and electronics at home that causes the students to listen and learn. In addition, students in the Montessori school have outdoor places that they visit that could help them gain

general knowledge, and in the non-Montessori schools students can learn from the teacher and the computer in class by exploring and watching. From my observation, the Montessori students go on fieldtrips more than the non-Montessori schools so they have the chance to explore and learn more.

Table 10 below shows that the mean of prediction and critical thinking score of Montessori pupils is 2.51 while the mean memory ability score of non-Montessori pupils is 2.44. The *t*-test was used to determine if there is a significant difference between the two groups. The *t*-test result shows a *p*-value of 0.78. This is greater than 0.05 which means that there is no significant difference between the critical thinking ability of the two groups.

Critical thinking can be gained in different ways by toys, or activities done in class, or by storytelling. As I have seen, in the non-Montessori school, the teacher tells the story by stopping taking their opinion of what might happen next or how they would resolve the problem. This improves students' critical thinking a lot, and it seems very helpful as I have observed it. The Montessori school concentrates more on reading and letting them read while telling a story, but they also have some toys for critical thinking, such as how to put the colored blocks in order like the picture on the box shows. Different ways produce good results, which made both schools have no significant difference in their results. Personally, I would use both approaches.

Table 10

Prediction/Critical Thinking Ability Mean Scores

School	Mean Scores
Montessori	2.51
Not-Montessori	2.44

As a conclusion, we were able to find out that there is no big difference between the schools facilities but there is a small difference in schools environments. This might be a cause why students of the Montessori school which had a better environment and more fieldtrips got better knowledge because they were able to explore more from real life not virtual life from technology. In addition, students in Montessori school got better grades in reading. I agree with Montessori for everyone (2017) that students learn how to read by writing, and that Montessori has some educational toys or the sand box that helps students trace letters. In addition, I agree that students should start reading signs on the road and students in Montessori might be offered these options more than the students in the non-Montessori school. Though the non-Montessori school has a sand box to write letters in, the Montessori school has touchable books that help students learn letters. However, critical thinking and memory were the same in both schools. Both schools students are being offered the opportunity to think critically and memorize information in one way or another.

The results are not all as expected but they were helpful. I expected that the Montessori school would be better than the non-Montessori school but because of this study I found that both schools were good even if they do not follow the same methodology or don't have the same facilities. Each school has its own way to teach. There are some points where the Montessori school does better than the non-Montessori, and in many of these, the non-Montessori school could improve and that would help in improving the students' results as well.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, I found out that both schools are good schools. They both taught their students fairly to get good grade. However, the Montessori school has a better physical environment for the students to visit and use for learning which improved some skills more than the students in the non-Montessori school. In addition, the Montessori school has facilities related to Montessori only whereas, non-Montessori had different facilities for learning to differentiate activities but both schools though different showed kind of the same results in students learning. These differences cause a little bit of difference in the test scores, both schools had no difference between their students' memory and prediction. However, Montessori students got better grades in reading and in general knowledge. Though the Lebanese curriculum does not force schools to follow a specific way of teaching or mandate how to divide teachings and make their students well educated, but these two schools are doing a great job in teaching their students reading, critical thinking, general knowledge and how to improve their memories.

Teachers differ just as students differ. Students learn differently, and teachers can teach differently. Both ways of teaching in these schools were good. Each had its own ups and downs. The results in actual learning slightly favored the Montessori approach, especially in the area of reading, but the differences were not large at all. The differences I observed were more important, especially those relating to the way students were engaged and paying attention in the Montessori classroom.

Answers to Research Questions

Below are the responses to the research questions asked at the beginning of this study.

1. What are the facilities, materials and methodologies like in a Montessori schools setting?

I was able to answer this question by doing some observations in a Montessori school. I found that the Montessori school had some manipulatives specially designed for their way of teaching. The Montessori school used a lot of toys/manipulatives, and books that help students learn letters using different senses. They also have a lot of outdoor activities. The description in the results section above shows what Montessori classes look like in detail.

2. Are there differences in the use of materials and methodologies between a school using Montessori and a school not using it?

There are differences between the two schools. Throughout my observations I was able to see many differences. The Montessori school makes sure to give the students the chance to explore and have real-life experiences more than the non-Montessori school by taking them to do outdoor activities and fieldtrips. Both schools are different in their activities. The Montessori school activities use more than two senses (seeing, listening, and touching) whereas, the non-Montessori school generally use only two senses (seeing and listening).

3. Are there differences in preschool student outcomes between a Montessori school and a non-Montessori school?

There were some differences in the outcomes between the two schools. Montessori students did better in the reading and the general knowledge part.

However, students from both schools did equally well on the critical thinking and memory ability part.

4. Do materials and the way they are used correlate with learning outcomes?

Montessori students did better in the reading and the general knowledge part. I believe that happened since they let their students explore more and use more than two senses to learn, which causes the students to gain more general knowledge, and using their senses to learn helps them read more letters.

However, students from both schools did equally well on the critical thinking and memory ability part. I believe that happened since both schools have some activities to improve these abilities, The Montessori school uses manipulatives/toys, whereas, the non-Montessori uses poems and stories.

Recommendations

After reading, observing and analyzing the methodologies of both schools I was able to see points that are so helpful for teaching, and others that need some improvement. So in the recommendation part, I will give some tips that I think these two schools should work on and improve.

1. The non-Montessori school should add some fieldtrips for the lessons taught. Even if they do not have outdoor spaces in the school, they can take the students out.
2. The non-Montessori school should get some more educational toys for the classroom to be used while playing and while teaching.
3. The non-Montessori school should add activities for reading by using different senses not only by listening to music so that students will become better readers.

4. The non-Montessori school should reduce the worksheet work and add some outdoor activities and exploration.
5. The Montessori school should give teachers some multimedia resources inside the class to facilitate their job while teaching.
6. The Montessori school should decrease the time of the lectures and add some hands-on activities integrated in the lesson not only while they give them time to play but also while explaining lessons.
7. The Lebanese curriculum should add more information about preschools since it is one of the most important stages in learning.

Questions for Further Research

This study has answered some basic questions, but raised many more. First of all, we did not see the differences that we might have expected to see in students' learning based on the differences in methodologies and materials.

1. Will we get the same results with schools following same study design but in different regions in Lebanon?
2. Can this study be replicated in schools with different socio-economic status and will the results stay the same?
3. If this study was done with a bigger group and more than two schools would the results have changed?
4. If both schools were using same books would we still have same results in reading? Is it the methodology or the books used?

5. If all schools followed the same rubrics of teaching and same curriculum would the students in both schools have same results or would it stay the same?

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APPENDIX A

CLASSROOM OBSERVATION FORM

Subject: _____ School: _____

Date and Time _____

Review Section	Description/Comments
<p>1. How does the teacher explain the lesson? (What does she use, is her class always student-centered or always teacher-centered?)</p>	
<p>2. Are the teachers prepared ahead of time? (Is she working smoothly or stops to read instructions, objectives, or anything and loose time rather than teaching)</p>	
<p>3. Does the teacher encourage her students and respect them? How does she treat them in general?</p>	
<p>4. Does the teacher use relevant teaching methods, aids, materials, techniques, and technology; include variety, balance, imagination, group involvement; use examples that are simple, clear, precise, and appropriate; stay focused on and meets stated objectives?</p>	
<p>5. Does the teacher encourage her students and respect them? How does she treat them in general?</p>	
<p>6. Does the teacher assist students with academic problems?</p>	

Review Section	Description/Comments
7. PHYSICAL ASPECTS OF CLASSROOM (How are the chairs and tables in class? How many students? What does the school environment look like? etc.	

Strengths observed:

Suggestions for improvement:

Overall impression of teaching effectiveness:

APPENDIX B

MATERIALS AVAILABILITY CHECKLIST

Facilities!	Super Adequate	Adequate	Inadequate	Not Available
1. Students have access to computers.				
2. Computers are available for teachers use.				
3. Availability of printing service				
4. Availability of photocopy machine in the school				
5. Availability of a TV set to be used for educational purposes				
6. Availability of a functional projector for educational purposes				
7. Is there an open area on the floor?				
8. Is there a storage unit such as bookshelves?				
9. Availability of a teacher assistant always in class				
10. Availability of educational toys(More than 10 in each class)				
11. The use of different centers in class				
12. Is there a teacher's desk?				
13. Availability of a play center?				
14. Quiet places to read.				
15. Availability of multimedia center.				
16. Play areas				
17. A space for children to store their work and personal belongings				
18. Availability of library services or a reading room.				
19. Availability of places students can visit for active learning (outdoor activities, parking lot)				
20. Bookstore				
21. Availability of different large playgrounds				
22. Availability of drama room, music room, dance room, art room.				
23. Availability of a music room.				
24. Availability of a dance room.				
25. Availability of an art room.				
26. Availability of fieldtrips on lessons taught.				
27. Availability of a big and safe sports room.				

APPENDIX D
PRIMARY ASSESSMENT

Memorization

What did you see on the desk?

Ending Sounds

Have the student name the picture in the box, and tell the ending sound he hears. Have him read the letter in the box naming that ending sound. Name the other pictures. Have him circle the pictures that end with the same sound as *boat*.

5

Ending Sounds (continued)

Have the student name the picture in the box, and tell the ending sound he hears. Have him read the letter in the box naming that ending sound. Name the other pictures. Have him circle the pictures that end with the same sound as *sun*.

Rhyming Words

Have the student name each picture. Then have him read the words in the box. Tell him to circle the word that rhymes with the picture name.

rug

red

met

mat

pit

pet

leg

dog

Predicting

Have the student cut out the pictures at the bottom of the page. Direct him/her to look at the picture in the first box with the star and decide what will happen next. Have him place in the space a picture that shows what will happen next. He should continue in the same manner with the other rows. Then have him paste the pictures.

<p>2.</p>	
<p>3.</p>	

General Knowledge

Circle the happy face if the sentence is correct and the sad face if the sentence is false.

1-

2-

3-

4-

5-

6-

General Knowledge Questions

1. A flower needs sun and water to grow. (happy)
2. All animals are wild animals. (sad)
3. Hamburger is healthy food. (sad)
4. There are four seasons in a year. (happy)
5. We have 6 senses. (sad)
6. Eggs grow in the garden. (sad)

MY RESUME

Nathalie J. Char

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Date of birth: July 30, 1992
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WORK EXPERIENCE

- **Private Tutor:**
2011 – current time
Tutoring private lessons (English, Math, Science, and Arabic).
KG3 till Grade 4
- **Teaching Observations:**
2012 and 2014 , 60 Hours at school.
Grade 3 Math classes
Grade 6 Math and Science classes
Adventist Secondary School – Bauchrieh
- **Work:**
KG3 Mother teacher since 2014 till Current time
- **Kids Animator and Teacher:**
2011-2012
Responsible for the Colony
Colony Saint Jean church – Dayshounieh

EDUCATION

- **2017:**
Master of arts in education: Educational Leadership.
Middle East University
- **2014:**
BA and TD in elementary education (Math and Sciences)
Middle East University
- **Honors and activities:** Honor list Spring 2012 GPA: 3.62 – Spring 2014 GPA: 3.76.
- **2010:**
Lebanese Baccalaureate, Economics and Sociology
Adventist Secondary School - Bauchrieh

PERSONAL PROFILE

- Languages : English Fluent, Arabic Fluent
- Computer skills: MS Office
- Fast learner in any field with great deal of enthusiasm and eagerness

INTERESTS

- Reading, voluntary work and sports.

REFERENCES

- References Available upon request.